

Quantum Mechanics and Deconstructing a Bound System

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A classical wave (such as one on a string, in water or air) is an entity with energy and momentum, which seems to exist due to an interaction with the medium. This leads to sinusoidal changes in the medium for a given pure E, p , $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$. In other words, there seems to be a kind of Newtonian action-reaction occurring, but one may think of a pure oscillation as having a particular energy and p . If various different E_i, p_i , are stirred up in the same medium and so exist at the same time, there are interactions with the medium of all of these pure waves, but they do not interact with each other or any kind of extra potential and so the energy identity should remain the same. If the energy of a single mode (or intensity) in the case of sound is proportional to $\sin(-\omega t + kx) * \sin(-\omega t + kx)$, then this same recipe should hold for: $Z = \sum_i \sin(-\omega_i t + k_i x)$, i.e. Z^2 . Upon integration over x, t , however, one should retrieve a sum of pure oscillation intensities which happens because $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$ are orthogonal. In such a case, one is mathematically deconstructing the physical waves interacting with the medium, described by Z , into a sum of intensities for each wave as if it existed by itself. The two results are identical.

A quantum mechanical bound state, we argue, is more complicated than this. First, we argued in (1) that one may obtain $-Et + px$ and the notion of a photon interacting in a periodic way with itself (its electric and magnetic fields) from special relativity. We suggested that the feature of $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ also holds for a particle with rest mass. In other words, the presence of E, p implies that there is a wavelike disturbance in terms of interaction (not center-of-mass motion). This wave, however, creates itself (photon) and involves forces which act over the wavelength, not at a center-of-mass point.

At first this seems like a deterministic viewpoint because a wave is deterministic. Given $-Et + px$, if one were to assume that it represents information, then $\ln(\text{probability}) = -Et + px \rightarrow \text{prob} = \exp(-Et + px)$. This, however, grows or decreases indefinitely and so one may alternatively propose $\exp(i(-Et + px))$. If $-Et + px$, however, is periodic in a deterministic manner, how can one suggest the presence of a probability in the first place? We suggest that there are two reasons. First, there are situations (like a 2-slit) which do not depend on time, but only on space. Secondly, $\exp(ipx)$ represents possible interactions in space, i.e. with different parts of the two slit apparatus, but an actual interaction only occurs at one x point, i.e. a single particle or photon receives a particular hit and changes its direction (not magnitude of p). The next particle or photon, undergoes a different angle changing hit etc, but these various angle changes are linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and hence it acts like a probability, but one which governs interactions. Actually $\exp(ipx)$ is like a conditional probability because p is known and one wants to know if a hit occurs at x with a 2-slit apparatus.

Thus, one goes beyond the classical wave because one has a self-wave which is no longer deterministic, but probabilistic in its interaction with a potential (e.g. 2-slit apparatus). In the classical wave picture, there is no such external potential or 2-slit if one just describes the wave. It is true that one may introduce a 2-slit apparatus for water waves and obtain interference, but this is physical interference through a medium which does not exist for the quantum particle.

We consider here the interaction of a quantum particle with rest mass with a potential. Unlike many physical modes on a string, different $\exp(ipx)$ are probabilities which exist at different times, but there is no time in the picture and so the probability picture is similar to adding various modes: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability, one may create averages: $\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \frac{p}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$. This average applies to a physical system in which interactions with $V(x)$ occur. Now $\frac{p}{2m}$ is a property of a single $\exp(ipx)$ even if it does interact with an extra potential. In such a case, one would have: $\frac{p}{2m} \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = \frac{p}{2m}$. Thus, each $\exp(ipx)$ brings its own $\frac{p}{2m}$ and one should be able to deconstruct the bound system. To do so, one must separate the various $\exp(ipx)$, just as in the sound wave intensity case. When the bound state is deconstructed, one has the sense of $P(p)$. For the bound state, one has a weight $a(p)$. The two do not need to be the same because they describe different physical systems. One involves interaction, the other does not, but is a consequence of deconstructing a system with interactions.

We suggest that the manner of deconstructing the interaction system $W(x)$ is to use orthogonality, i.e.

$$\int dx W^*(x) \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a^*(p)a(p) \frac{p}{2m}$$

Thus, one has a deconstructed state. We explain in detail how the above equation is obtained. We suggest that $a^*(p)a(p) = P(p)$ and $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ are linked with deconstructed states as one breaks the bound state in obtaining these measurements. We discuss the reason that $P(p)$ contains no information about x and $P(x)$, about p .

Classical Wave

A classical wave exists in a medium. It is created by a force and, given the existence of the medium, an action-reaction process with the medium seems to continue in time and space, leading to the notion of a wave which has energy and momentum. Examples include waves on a string, water and sound in air and other media. A pure wave is described sinusoidally by $A \sin(-\omega t + kx)$ where ω is angular frequency and $k = 2\pi / \text{wavelength}$. We argue that such a wave is deterministic in x, t .

Special Relativity, Photons and Quantum Mechanics

We argued in (1) that the equations of special relativity require the presence of an upper bound speed, c , which is the same as seen by all constant moving frames. This means that it is not associated with a rest mass and should be linked with properties of space. We argued in (1), that c is the speed of light and noted that Maxwell's equations (strongly linked to special relativity) show that one may have an electric and magnetic field sinusoidal wave $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$ which is also deterministic. The electric and magnetic fields allow for force interactions with charged particles (as in 2-slit apparatus) and at the same time are linked with E and p , i.e. $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$.

We suggested that since the equations of special relativity, written in terms of E, p , hold for both a photon and particle with rest mass, then this property should hold for both as well. At this

point, there is no notion of probability. At best, one has a self-wave created in the photon case by an electric and magnetic field which act like a kind of medium and represent action-reaction as well.

The Case for $-Et+px$ Being Linked with Probability

We argued that in the photon case, the wavelength implies that the electric and magnetic fields may interact in different ways across a wavelength. This leads to possible interactions with two slits separated by about a wavelength instead of an interaction occurring at a center-of-mass point. We suggest that a periodic $-Et+px$ may be considered as being a probability for two reasons:

- (A) One may remove time from some problems, such as 2-slit apparatus. Two particles with $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ have different speeds (times), but produce the same 2-slit interference pattern.
- (B) $\exp(ipx)$ describes possible hits in space with a 2-slit apparatus, but only one interaction occurs, i.e. a particle has its angle changed in only one way based on the probability $\exp(ipx)$. One requires many particles (sent in one at a time) to see all of the angular changes.

If probability is required, then one may use: $\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information} = -Et+px$ ((1))

This leads to $\text{Prob} = \exp(-Et+px)$, but this grows or drops indefinitely so:

$$\text{Prob} = \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((2))$$

As a result, one no longer has the deterministic situation of the classical wave or even the photon with its periodic electric and magnetic fields, but a probabilistic picture, with $\exp(ipx)$ describing an interaction. $\exp(ipx)$, however still retains the identity of:

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \text{ and momentum} = p \text{ (Nonrelativistic case)} \quad ((3))$$

In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability which arises from a kind of self-wave being created (by electric and magnetic fields in the photon case) which probabilistically interacts with points in space, i.e. an external potential which does not exist for a set of pure classical waves (although may be introduced).

(We argue later that $\exp(ipx)$ is actually a conditional probability because one knows p and wants to know if a hit occurs at x .)

As a result, a bound quantum problem must be described in terms of $\exp(ipx)$. If $V(x)$ represents energy, then one requires the kinetic energy present. If one has a single particle, then its probabilities are:

$$\exp(ip_1x) \text{ or } \exp(ip_2x) \text{ or } \exp(ip_3x) \text{ etc} \quad ((4))$$

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Average kinetic energy is:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((6)) \text{ and}$$

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

We note that in ((6)), $p^2/2m$ is the kinetic energy of a free particle, but still appears in the case of an interacting one with $\exp(ipx)$ existing over a range of x . This kinetic energy represents a property of a free particle and so one should be able to physically deconstruct ((6)) to find the classical probability weight $P(p)$ which is not the same as $a(p)$ (due to the fact that $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is a conditional probability). In fact, it seems that one must use orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$'s to deconstruct ((6)). We argue that deconstructing ((6)) actually means breaking an ensemble of bound states and so one now has a new physical system, i.e. a set of free particles. Multiplying ((6)) by $W^*(x)W(x)$ seems to allow for the deconstruction:

$$\int dx KE_{ave}(x) W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_i p^2/2m a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((8))$$

Then, $W^*(x)W(x)$ may physically be identified as $P(x)$. ((9))

While the particle is interacting, one does not think in terms of a free probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ or a free density $W^*(x)W(x)$, but uses the interacting probability $\exp(ipx)$. $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ represents the amount of time that a particle spends in dx and this has nothing to do with an interaction which is based on $\exp(ipx)$.

To see this in more detail, $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is a conditional probability (to have p if you are at x). It must be multiplied by $P(x)$, the probability to be at x . The integral over x must deconstruct the result, meaning that it must make use of the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s. If one wishes to have $P(x)$, then we argued that it equals $W^*(x)W(x)$. In other words, $W^*(x)$ is the time reversed state of $W(x)$ and undoes motion in x (the self-wave linked with forces). For $\exp(-iEt+ipx)\exp(iEt-ipx)=1$, one has no spatial or time dependence, but $W^*(x)W(x)$ will show x dependence for a bound state. Thus, the idea of orthogonality, time reversal and conditional probability appear in obtaining:

$$P(p) = a^*(p)a(p) \text{ and } P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((10))$$

Given that one uses a conditional probability $P(p/x)$ multiplied by $P(x)$ to obtain $P(p)$, it cannot have any information about x . If one wishes to know $P(p/x)$, it is complex because it follows from the self-wave which has probabilistic hits with $V(x)$ or a 2-slit target etc. Its weight is $a(p)$. Given that a p hit occurs within a wavelength in a probabilistic manner, it does not seem to make sense to ask about a free particle probability for p at x . Similarly, $W^*(x)W(x)$ includes all p values. The fact that one has to write:

$P(p/x) P(x)$ ((11))

means that one is not focused on the interaction which only uses $P(p/x)$ as in ((7)). One is only considering $\exp(ipx)$ probabilistic hits with $V(x)$ at each x using $a(p)$ as a weight for each $\exp(ipx)$. $P(x)$, the probability to be at x , seems to be linked with the amount of time a single particle spends at each dx , but this is irrelevant for an interaction based on $V(x)$ which does not involve time. The same holds for a 2-slit apparatus.

Conclusion

Special relativity yields equations in E and p which apply equally well to a particle with rest mass as to a photon (e.g. $-Et+px = -E't' + p'x'$ and $E^2 - pc^2 = 0$). A photon is known to be a kind of self-wave created by deterministically changing electric and magnetic fields perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion. These changes are based on $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$ where $E = \hbar \omega$ and $p = \hbar k$. Thus, the electric and magnetic fields are like a medium, but also represent force and so this force is changing in x and t leading to 2-slit interference results. A similar feature should hold for a particle with rest mass because the special relativistic equations above apply to both, i.e. $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$.

The photon wave ($\sin(-\omega t + kx)$) features of the electric and magnetic fields are deterministic, so why should one consider a probabilistic theory (free particle quantum mechanics) associated with them? We argue that interaction in space often does not involve time (e.g. a 2-slit apparatus experiment). Then, $\exp(ipx)$ shows that even with time gone, one does not know which x point results in an impulse hit. Thus, the scenario is probabilistic, but not random, as it is governed by $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ represents an interaction conditional probability and should be used in a problem with a potential $V(x)$, i.e. a bound state problem. In such a case, $V(x)$ means that at x one has a certain potential value, but $\exp(ipx)$ is a conditional kind of probability because it represents a given p , but unknown x . Thus, it is linked with $P(p/x)$. This means that to find $P(p)$ one needs $\sum_x P(p/x) P(x)$, but one actually solves an interaction problem using $P(p/x)$.

We suggest that in such a case, one must deconstruct $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ using orthogonality. Given: $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, this suggests that $W^*(x)W(x)$ suffices. Here $W^*(x)$ is the time reverse of $W(x)$ which removes the interaction motion of $\exp(ipx)$ and makes use of orthogonality when one integrates.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Space-time Intervals Associated with Momentum and Energy? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)